

PREPARATION AND UV-AGEING RESISTANCE PROPERTIES OF POLY(P-PHENYLENE BENZOBISOXAZOLE)/NANO-TiO₂ NANOCOMPOSITE FIBERS

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ABSTRACT

Poly(p-phenylene benzobisoxazole) (PBO) fibers are so characterized by their high performance such as excellent mechanical properties, good thermal stability and environmental stability that they are optimum materials for harsh environmental conditions in the fields of aerospace, military and general industry. PBO fibers, however, have some critical problems such as photodegradation under UV exposure which limit their applications. Particularly, UV degradation posed a serious challenge for the development of PBO-based products. For the purpose of improving the poor ultraviolet-ageing resistance of PBO fiber, nanocomposite fibers of PBO and nanotitania(TiO₂) were prepared via in situ polymerization in poly(phosphoric acid)(PPA). In situ synthesis of PBO/n-TiO₂ nanocomposites were carried out in three stages: (1) dehydrochlorination, (2) polymerization, and (3) heterocyclization. At the beginning of the polymerization stage, additional P₂O₅ was added into the reactant to increase the concentration P₂O₅ in PPA from 80 wt% (preferable to TPA solubility) to 87 wt% (preferable to PBO solubility). In all the polymerization, solid content of PBO in PPA was maintained as 14 wt% for direct spinning of the as-polymerization solution. The PBO and PBO/n-TiO₂ nanocomposite fibers were dry-jet wet spun by a piston-driven system with a 4-hole spinneret (hole diameter: 0.2 mm). The liquid crystalline solution at 140 °C was extruded through the air gap of 10 cm to a coagulation bath filled with 5 wt% aqueous phosphoric acid at room temperature. UV-ageing tests for the PBO and PBO/n-TiO₂ fibers were performed by using a box equipped with UV lamps emitting 300~500 nm for 8~16 h. It was found that the composite fibers exhibited much improved UV-ageing resistance presumably due to UV blocking effect by n-TiO₂ from the SEM and TEM observations.

1 INTRODUCTION

PBO fibers are so characterized by their high performance such as excellent mechanical properties, good thermal stability and environmental stability that they are optimum materials for harsh environmental conditions such as high temperature, humidity, harmful strong chemicals, high-energy solar radiation, variations in air pressure, abrasion from external sources, etc. in the fields of aerospace, military and general industry [1-3].

PBO fibers, however, have some critical problems such as weak compressive properties and photo-degradation under UV exposure which limit their applications [6-13]. Particularly, UV degradation posed a serious challenge for the development of PBO-based products. Much effort has been attempted to enhance UV-ageing resistance including formation of crosslinking bonds in the chemical structure [9, 10], usage of organic and inorganic UV absorbers [11, 12] and fiber surface coating [13].

On the other hand, it has been reported that nan-titania(TiO₂) is very effective in enhancing UV resistance in polymers as well as cosmetics.

In this study, a series of PBO nanocomposites having n- TiO₂ were synthesized for the purpose of improving UV-ageing resistance. The effect of n- TiO₂ in PBO on the retention of tensile properties after UV exposure were investigated for the PBO and the nanocomposite fibers spun at a liquid crystalline state through a dry-jet wet spinning. The effect of n-TiO₂ on the molecular

weight, formation of liquid crystalline solution, surface and inner fibril morphology were also studied.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

The first page must contain the Title, Author(s), Affiliation(s), Key words and the Summary. The Introduction must begin immediately below, following the format of this template. 4,6-Diaminoresorcinol dihydrochloride (DAR-2HCl) were supplied by Zhejiang Dragon Co. (China) and TCI Chemical Co., respectively. Terephthalic acid (TPA), tin(II) chloride dehydrate and methanesulfonic acid (MSA) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Co. Phosphorus pentoxide (P_2O_5) and poly (phosphoric acid) (PPA) with P_2O_5 content of 80 wt% were provided by Sinopharm Chemical Reagent Co. (China). Commercial Degussa P25 nano- TiO_2 (average particle size: 21 nm) was supplied. All chemicals were used directly without any further treatment except TPA, which was ground to the finer powder form using an IKA blade mill followed by sieving with a mesh of $53\mu m$. As shown in scheme 1, PBO and its copolymers was synthesized from DAR-2HCl, TPA and NDCA in the PPA solvent based on the Wolfe's method. As the recipe and conditions for the syntheses summarized in Table 1, 8.52 g (40 mmol) of DAR-2HCl, 7.14 g(43 mmol) of the sieved TPA, 37.37 g PPA and 0.21 g(2.4 mol%) $SnCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ were placed in a 500 ml three-necked round-bottom glass flask equipped with a mechanical stirrer under purging of nitrogen gas. A series of PBO/ nano- TiO_2 nanocomposites were prepared.

As depicted in Figure 1 and Table 1, the synthesis of PBO were carried out in three stages: (1) dehydrochlorination of DAR-2HCl at $60\text{ }^\circ C$ for 4 h and subsequently at $80\text{ }^\circ C$ for 4 h, (2) polymerization at $110\text{ }^\circ C$ for 7 h and $150\text{ }^\circ C$ for 6 h, and (3) heterocyclization at $190\text{ }^\circ C$ for 12 h. At the beginning of the polymerization stage, additional P_2O_5 was added into the reactant to increase the concentration P_2O_5 in PPA ($=P_2O_5 + H_2O$) from 80 wt% (preferable to TPA solubility) to 87 wt% (preferable to PBO solubility). In all the polymerization, solid content of PBO in PPA was maintained as 14 wt% for direct spinning of the as-polymerization solution. During the synthesis, nitrogen gas was purged with a constant stirring.

Figure 1. Profiles of temperature and PPA concentration during polymerization.

Table 1. In situ Polymerization conditions of PBO and PBO/n-TiO₂ nanocomposites

Polymer Code	DAR (mmol)	TPA (mmol)	TiO ₂ (wt%)	SnCl ₂ (wt%)	Concentration of PPA (P ₂ O ₅ %)	Solid Content of PBO in PPA (wt%)
PBO	40.0	40.0	0.0	1.5	80.0->87.0	14.0
PBO-0.5wt% TiO ₂			0.5			
PBO-1.0wt% TiO ₂			1.0			

※ Weight % of SnCl₂ and TiO₂ are based on PBO.

The as-polymerized solutions of PBO and PBO/nano-TiO₂ nanocomposite were dry-jet wet spun by a piston-driven system with a 4-hole spinneret (hole diameter: 0.2 mm), as depicted in Figure 2. The liquid crystalline solution at 140 °C was extruded through the air gap of 10 cm to a coagulation bath filled with 20 wt% aqueous phosphoric acid at room temperature. Finally, the fibers were taken-up on a plastic spool. The obtained fiber was dipped in a large volume of distilled water for 24 h to remove the residual solvent completely followed by drying at 80 °C for 12 h. The conditions of spinning were summarized in Table 2.

Figure 2. Dry-jet wet spinning process.

Table 2. Spinning conditions

Fiber Code	Spinning Temp. (°C)	Spinneret Diameter /Length (mm)	Air Gap (cm)	Coagulation		Spinning Speed (V ₀) m/min	Take-up Speed (V _t) m/min	Spinning Draw Ratio (SDR) (V _t /V ₀)
				1 st vertical bath	2 nd horizontal bath			
PBO	140	0.2/20 4holes	5	5 wt% PA	Just water	0.9	33.0	36.6
PBO-0.5wt% TiO ₂								
PBO-1.0wt% TiO ₂								

The ultraviolet irradiation of the PBO fibers were performed by locating the fibers under the UV lamps (400 W) equipped in a lab-made box. The UV source was M400 which radiates UV with wavelength range of 300-500 nm. The specimens were fixed at the same position in the box for 8 and 16 h.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Synthesis of PBO and PBO/n-TiO₂ nanocomposites

Generally it is essential to use an exact stoichiometry in polycondensation, that is the equal moles of the two monomers in order to obtain polymers of high molecular weight. As PBO synthesis is not a homogeneous solution system but heterogeneous system due to poor solubility of TPA in PPA, whereas the solubility of DAR·2HCl is much better than that of TPA in PPA, excess TPA by 1.5 mol% than DAR·2HCl. Due to this poor solubility of TPA in PPA, the particle size of TPA is a key point in obtaining high molecular weight of PBO. Thus, TPA was ground and sieved with a mesh of 53um which enabled to obtain polymers with reasonable molecular weight to make fiber spinning. Table 3 shows the intrinsic viscosities and molecular weights of the PBO and PBO/n-TiO₂ nanocomposites. It can be noted that the effect of n-TiO₂ on the molecular weight was negligible in this study.

Table 3. Intrinsic viscosities & molecular weights of PBO and PBO/n-TiO₂ nanocomposites

Polymer Code	Intrinsic Viscosity (dl/g)	Molecular Weight (g/mol)
PBO	23.3	25282
PBO-0.5wt% TiO ₂	23.9	25642
PBO-1.0wt% TiO ₂	24.4	25926

3.2 Preparation and structural characterization of PBO and PBO/n-TiO₂ nanocomposite fibers

Figure 3 shows optical micrographs of PBO and PBO/n-TiO₂ nanocomposites solutions in PPA at 140°C under a polarizing optical microscope at cross-Nicol state. Liquid crystalline state was clearly observed at the temperature where spinning was performed. As-polymerized solutions of not only PBO but all the PBO/n-TiO₂ nanocomposites exhibited the same anisotropic state which is essential for making high performance fibers.

3.3 Effect of nan-TiO₂ on UV-ageing resistance of PBO fibers

UV-ageing resistance of PBO and its nanocomposite fibers was evaluated via retention of tensile strength and diameter reduction using UTM and optical microscope, respectively. Figure 4(a) shows the effect of UV exposure time on the tensile strength of PBO and PBO/n-TiO₂ nanocomposites fibers. It could be obviously observed that PBO fiber is very vulnerable to UV showing more than 50% loss in the strength after 16 h irradiation. However, the PBO/n-TiO₂ nanocomposites fibers exhibited improved retention of tensile strength compared to that of homo-PBO fiber after UV exposure. It was found that 0.5 wt% of nano-TiO₂ was enough for improving of tensile strength retention. Little improvement by 1.0wt% of nano-TiO₂ was exhibited compared to the case of 0.5wt% content.

On the other hand, it was also found that there was significant reduction in the fiber diameters. Figure 4(b) represents the change of the reduction of fiber diameters with addition of nan-TiO₂ and UV exposure time. Change of diameter reduction was tested and averaged by using 50 specimens for the each kind of sample at every UV exposure test. It is notable that the diameter of PBO fibers was decreased in proportion to UV exposure time, which implies a kind of etching was occurred by UV

from the surface of the fibers. From the figure, it can be seen that the nano-TiO₂ effect on the reduction of fiber diameter is very significant.

Figure 3. Representative liquid crystalline states of as-synthesized PBO and PBO/n-TiO₂ nanocomposite solutions at 140 °C under a polarizing microscope.

Figure 4. Change of tensile strength retention and diameter of PBO and PBO-NDCA fibers according to UV exposure time.

3.4 Surface morphology characterization of PBO and PBO/n-TiO₂ nanocomposite fibers

Figure 5 shows the surface microstructures of PBO and PBO/n-TiO₂ nanocomposite fibers before and after UV-ageing. Contrary to the smooth surface of PBO and PBO/n-TiO₂ nanocomposite, the UV-aged fibers showed rougher surfaces with lots of bumps as well as reduced diameter. To further explore the improvement of anti-UV degradation ability of PBO-NDCA fibers, AFM was performed. The 3-dimensional topography AFM images of PBO and PBO-9mol%NDCA fibers before and after

UV-ageing are shown in Figure 8 (a) and (b). It also exhibits the surface of PBO-NDCA fibers are much glossier and smoother than that of PBO fibers after UV-ageing.

Figure 5. SEM images of PBO (a) and PBO/n-TiO₂ fibers before and after UV irradiation for 16 h.

4 CONCLUSIONS

PBO nanocomposites with 1.5-3.0 wt% TiO₂ have been successfully prepared through in-situ polymerization. TPA size effect was very critical in obtaining high molecular weight due to its poor solubility in PPA. PBO and PBO/TiO₂ fibers could be obtained by dry-jet wet spinning the as-polymerized solutions at a liquid crystalline state. It was found that nano-TiO₂ were significantly effective in improving UV-ageing resistance.

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